

benzothiazole system is also known to possess anti-cancer activity. The preparation and characterization of four derivatives of this system are reported in this communication.

Pharmacology: Preliminary testing has shown that these compounds possess considerable antitumor activity. Details of antitumor activity and other biological activities will be published elsewhere.

Fig. 1.

1) **3-Ethylthio-7-nitro-S-triazole (3,4-b) benzothiazole:**

6-Nitro-2-amino benzothiazole was prepared by Hegerschoffs³ method and was converted into nitro-2-chlorobenzothiazole by Sandmayer's reaction^{4,5}. The yield varied from 40–60%. The chlorocompound was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol for 3 to 4 hr. The yellow crystalline compound, 6-nitro-2-hydrazino benzothiazole was separated and recrystallised from 95% ethanol. This compound (4.0 g) was suspended in alcohol (1 : 15) and excess of carbondisulphide added and mixture refluxed for 8 hr. The solution was cooled and the solid separated was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. 2.0 g of 7-nitro-3-mercapto-S-triazole (3,4-b) benzothiazole was suspended in alcohol. 0.8 g of KOH and 5 ml of ethyl iodide were added. The mixture was refluxed for 45 min, cooled and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated and the residue was recrystallised from alcohol which gave 3-ethylthio-7-nitro (3,4-b) benzothiazole (1.9 g; m.p. 195°–196°). Found: C, 42.64; H, 2.65; C₁₀H₈S₂N₄O₂ requires C, 42.84; H, 2.87%.

2) **3-Ethylthio-7-methoxy-2-phenyl-S-triazole (3,4-b) benzothiazole:**

6-Methoxy-2-chlorobenzothiazole was prepared using *p*-anisidine and adopting the procedure given for 6-nitro-2-chloro benzothiazole. 8 g of 2-chloro compound was refluxed with phenyl hydrazine hydrochloride in ethanol for 3 to 4 hr. The colourless compound 2-phenylhydrazino benzothiazole was separated and recrystallised from 95% ethanol. 8 g of this compound was suspended in alcohol (1 : 15), excess of carbon disulphide added and the mixture refluxed for 8 hr. The solid was separated by filtration. 7-Methoxy-3-mercapto-2-phenyl-S-triazole benzothiazole (4 g) was suspended in alcohol, 1.2 g potassium hydroxide and 5 ml of ethyl iodide were added. The mixture was refluxed for 45 min,

cooled and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated and the residue on crystallization gave colourless crystals of 3-ethylthio-7-methoxy-2-phenyl-S-triazole (3,4-b) benzothiazole (4.3 g; m.p. 130°). Found: C, 51.50; H, 4.21; C₁₆H₁₆S₂N₃OCl requires C, 51.82; H, 4.06%.

3) **3-Ethylthio-7-chloro-S-triazole (3,4-b) benzothiazole:**

This was prepared from 6-chloro-2-hydrazino benzothiazole using the procedure given for the preparation of compound No. 1. It is a colourless crystalline solid, m.p. 195°. Found: C, 44.67; H, 2.61; C₁₀H₈S₂N₃Cl requires C, 44.50; H, 2.98%.

4) **3-Methylthio-7-chloro-S-triazole (3,4-b) benzothiazole**

This was prepared following the procedure given for compound No. 1. The 3-mercapto compound was treated with potassium hydroxide and methyl iodide which gave light brown crystalline compound, m.p. 173°. Found: C, 42.10; H, 2.10. C₉H₆S₂N₃Cl requires C, 42.26; H, 2.36%.

The compounds exhibited peaks in the I.R. spectrum at 1410, 3100, 3060, 1600, 1510, 1500 characteristic of S-CH₃ asy. def; CH (aromatic), C=C and C=N respectively. λ Max were observed at 230, 254, 285 and 310 in support of the above conclusions.

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Extraction and direct spectrophotometric determination of palladium with potassium ethyl xanthate

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THE xanthate compounds have been used as reagents for extraction of a number of metals¹. Chakraborty and De² used potassium ethyl xanthate for the extraction of arsenic(III), antimony(III) and bismuth(III). Rao and Sing³ extracted Cu(II),

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Co(II), Ni(III) and Bi(III) into pyridine-ethylacetate mixture (1 : 4) using the same reagent. Likewise the same pattern Mukherjee^{4,5} extracted lead and zinc into carbon tetrachloride. In our laboratory potassium ethyl xanthate has been used to extract palladium followed by spectrophotometric determination. Our previous communications⁶⁻⁸ show the use of other xanthates to determine palladium.

Experimental

An aliquot (2 ml) of palladium chloride stock solution containing 4.7 mg of Pd(II) was mixed with a calculated volume of hydrochloric acid of known strength to give the desired acid concentration and diluted with distilled water to 15 ml. The aqueous solution thus prepared was then shaken for 10 min with 10 ml of 1% xanthate in chloroform. To study the effect of pH different buffer solutions were used. The amount of palladium extracted was directly obtained from a previously prepared calibration curve.

Palladium is quantitatively extracted from 10(M) HCl media to pH 8.0.

Results and Discussion

Absorption curve :

The spectrum of Pd(II)-potassium ethyl xanthate complex in chloroform extracted as above shows a strong absorbance at 410 nm which falls steadily at 440 nm and then shows a maximum absorbance at 465 nm, becomes insignificant beyond 520 nm. The reagent itself shows practically no absorbance from 410 nm onwards. All the absorbance measurements were performed at 465 nm against a reagent blank. The colour is stable at least for 12 hr.

Period of extraction and reagent concentration :

The shaking period varies depending upon the acidity of the aqueous phase used. In strong acid medium the shaking period is 5 min which increases with decrease in acid concentration; e.g., in 1(M) HCl medium the safety margin is 10 min and at pH 8.0 the required time is about 30-40 min. The optimum reagent concentration is 10 ml chloroform solution of the xanthate (1%).

Effect of acidity :

Extraction behaviour of Pd(II)-xanthate system was studied over the acidic range of 10(M) to 1(M) HCl as well as the pH range 1.0 to 8.0. Palladium is quantitatively extracted from this whole range.

Molar absorptivity and sensitivity :

Molar absorptivity of the complex is 1.9×10^2 litre mole⁻¹cm⁻¹ at 465 nm (on the basis of the palladium content) and sensitivity according to Sandell's definition is 0.0058 mg.

Nature of the complex :

The empirical formula of the potassium ethyl xanthate complex of palladium was determined by

the mole ratio method. The results indicate that the metal to reagent ratio in the complex is 1 : 2.

Interference :

The interference was judged by carrying out the extraction at 1(M) HCl media unless otherwise stated. The preliminary study of the effect of diverse ions on the extraction shows that Pd(II) can safely be determined in presence of 15-fold excess of the followings : Li(I), Be(II), Mg(II), Ca(II), Ba(II), Sr(II), La(III), Ce(III), Zr(IV), Cr(III), W(VI), Mn(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Al(III), Sb(III), Th(IV), U(VI), Fe(III), Pb(II), Ni(II), Co(II), and Cu(II). Interferences due to iron and lead may be overcome by performing the extraction in presence of ammonium bifluoride and sodium acetate respectively. At higher acidities sodium acetate fails to mask lead as PbCl₂ is precipitated. Nickel and cobalt were masked with EDTA. In presence of Cu(II), extraction requires 10(M) HCl medium as copper is strongly extracted at lower acidities. Bismuth shows strong colour interference. Gold is precipitated during operation and hinders the procedure.

Among the other platinum metals rhodium(III) and ruthenium(III) do not interfere in the ratio of Pd(II) : metal as 1 : 5. Presence of Pt(IV) always produces high results as it is co-extracted due to its intense similarity in properties with palladium. Osmium(VIII) produces a deep brown solution and hence must be absent. This is done by a preliminary extraction with hexamethylene tetramine into chloroform in presence of EDTA. Palladium is retained in the aqueous phase while osmium migrates into the organic layer. Palladium may then be extracted as usual. Anions like citrate, tartrate, acetate, borate, phosphate, EDTA, oxalate, sulfate, bromide, iodide, thiocyanate, arsenate do not interfere in weight ratios of 1 : 25. High concentration of thiosulfate results incomplete extraction. Interferences of vanadate and molybdate may be avoided if the extraction be conducted at pH 8.0.

Reproducibility :

The results are accurate to within $\pm 2.5\%$. Thus the proposed method is fairly precise and reproducible. The process is rapid and simple. The total operation for each run requires only 20-25 min.

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Estimation of linuron residues in some fodder crops and soils*

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LINURON (N-3,4-dichlorophenyl-N'-methoxy-N'-methyl urea) has been successfully used as a selective herbicide for the control of many annual grasses and broadleaf weeds in a variety of fodder and food crops enabling higher agricultural productivity. Estimation of herbicide residues in treated crops and soils becomes imperative to ensure that these, if present are well within the prescribed tolerance and are non-hazardous either to consumer or to subsequent crop. Methods for residues determination reported by Lowen and Baker¹; Bleidner² and Bleidner³ *et al* consisted of hydrolytic-decomposition of linuron and quantitative estimation of the liberated N, O-dimethyl hydroxyl amine and 3,4-dichloroaniline respectively. Kirkland⁴ described a gas chromatographic technique using flame ionization detector. In the present communication, we describe a simple, accurate and reproducible colorimetric method for the extraction and determination of linuron residues in sunflower, oats, soyabean fodders, wheat grains and straws and soils. The method consists of quantitative conversion of linuron to 3,4-dichloroaniline which, on diazotization with nitrous acid and coupling with alkaline β -naphthol solution forms a red dye. The absorbance of the dye dissolved in methanol is measured at 540 nm in a photoelectric colorimeter against methanol (40%) as blank. The sampling, extraction, hydrolysis, purification, chromatographic clean-up procedures have been discussed.

Experimental

Standard curve: Calibration curve was prepared in terms of 3,4-dichloroaniline (DCA). A solution of DCA in 0.1N hydrochloric acid (0.01 mg DCA per ml) was used. 0.4, 0.8, 1.2, 1.6, 2.0 and 2.4 ml DCA solutions were taken in six test tubes and the volume in each was made to 2.4 ml by adding requisite quantity of hydrochloric acid (0.1 N). 0.5 ml sodium nitrite solution (1.4%) was added to each tube and the reaction completed in ten minutes.

Excess of sodium nitrite was destroyed by the addition of 0.5 ml ammonium sulphamate solution (8%). After 5 min 1 ml β -naphthol solution (100 mg dissolved in 100 ml of 2% potassium hydroxide) was added and allowed to stand for 10 min. The contents of the test tubes were thoroughly mixed after addition of each reagent. Finally 2 ml methanol was added which dissolved the dye producing a transparent solution. The absorbance was measured at 540 nm against methanol (40%) as blank. The concentration of DCA was plotted against optical density and the amount of herbicide calculated (0.01 mg DCA = 0.0154 mg linuron).

Sampling and extraction: Freshly harvested plant samples (200–500 g) were made homogeneous to a fine pulp in a blender, mixed with celite (15–20 g) and transferred to a Soxhlet extractor with acetone. The extraction was continued for 4 hr. Acetone was distilled at diminished pressure and the extractive was refluxed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide (20%; 100 ml) for 3 hr. The contents were allowed to cool to room temperature and made acidic (pH 2) with hydrochloric acid. Alcohol was distilled off and the hydrolysate transferred to a 500 ml separating funnel and made alkaline (pH 10) with potassium hydroxide solution (10%). It was extracted with three successive 200 ml portions of ether. The ether extract was washed free of alkali with distilled water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and carefully concentrated to about 50 ml.

Chromatographic clean-up: The coloured interferences were removed from the ether extract by chromatography over a column of neutral alumina Brockmann's grade. The column (40 × 1.5 cm) fitted with the stopcock was prepared by putting a plug of glass wool at the base of the column and alumina was introduced as slurry in a mixture of petroleum ether and ether (1 : 1) taking care that no air bubble could remain in the column. The top of the column was covered with a thin padding of glass wool. The ether extract and its washings were poured over the column which was eluted with a mixture of petroleum ether and ether (1 : 2). The eluate (150 ml) was collected in a separating funnel and extracted with hydrochloric acid (0.1N) thrice in succession (20, 10, 10 ml). The acid extract was taken in a 50 ml volumetric flask. The flask was gently heated on a water bath at 45° for 10 min to drive off the dissolved solvent ether and after cooling made to volume with hydrochloric acid (0.1N). The DCA was estimated colorimetrically as above.

Determination of herbicide in plant and soil samples fortified with known amounts of linuron gave uniform recoveries. The method could be used for estimation of linuron residues in sunflower, oats, soyabean fodders, wheat grains and straws and soils. The lower limit of determination being 1 ppm linuron.

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